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A STABILITY INDICATING METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF OFLOXACIN AND METRONIDAZOLE IN BULK AND DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole in bulk and dosage form by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole by using Qualisil BDS C18 column, flow rate was 1ml/min, mobile phase ratio was Methanol: ACN (70:30%v/v), detection wave length was 254nm. The linearity study for Ofloxacin and Metronidazole was found in concentration range of 10µg-50µg and 10µg-50µg and correlation coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, for the amount of drugs estimated by the proposed methods was in good agreement with the label claim. The proposed methods were validated. The accuracy of the methods was assessed by recovery studies at three different levels. Recovery experiments indicated the absence of interference from commonly encountered pharmaceutical additives. The method was found to be precise as indicated by the repeatability analysis, showing %RSD less than 2. All statistical data proves validity of the methods, sensitivity, precision and reproducibility. It can be used for routine analysis of pharmaceutical dosage form. Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

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INTRODUCTION OFLOXACIN

FIG-1

Chemical Data

IUPAC Name:

7-fluoro-2-methyl-6-(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)-10-oxo-4-oxa-1-azatricyclo[7.3.1.0^{5,13}]trideca-5(13),6,8,11-tetraene-11-carboxylic acid

Chemical formula:

C₁₈H₂₀FN₃O₄

Molecular weight:

361.3675

Physical Data

Description:

This compound belongs to the class of organic compounds known as quinoline carboxylic acids. These are quinolines in which the quinoline ring system is substituted by a carboxyl group at one or more positions.

Category:

Anti-Bacterial Agents, Anti-Infective Agents

Mechanism of action

Ofloxacin acts on DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, enzymes which, like human topoisomerase, prevents the excessive supercoiling of DNA during replication or transcription. By inhibiting their function, the drug thereby inhibits normal cell division.

METRONIDAZOLE

FIG-2.

Chemical Data

IUPAC Name:

2-(2-methyl-5-nitro-1H-imidazol-1-yl)ethan-1-ol

Chemical formula:

C₆H₉N₃O₃

Molecular weight:

171.154

Physical Data**Description:**

A nitroimidazole used to treat amebiasis; vaginitis; trichomonas infections; giardiasis; anaerobic bacteria; and treponemal infections. It has also been proposed as a radiation sensitizer for hypoxic cells. According to the Fourth Annual Report on Carcinogens, this substance may reasonably be anticipated to be a carcinogen.

Solubility:

Soluble in water and methanol

Category:

Alimentary Tract and Metabolism, Anti-Infective Agent

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Metronidazole is a prodrug. Unionized metronidazole is selective for anaerobic bacteria due to their ability to intracellularly reduce metronidazole to its active form. This reduced metronidazole then covalently binds to DNA, disrupt its helical structure, inhibiting bacterial nucleic acid synthesis and resulting in bacterial cell death.

The existing literature review shows that HPLC and derivative spectroscopic methods have been carried out. However there is a need to develop an easier and cost effective RP HPLC method development which can be carried out on small scale laboratory basis also. Hence by observing literature, this work is carried out to obtain a low retention time, and an easier and cost effective method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**MATERIALS:**

The list of instruments used in the course of experimental work is as follows:

Table-1 List of Instruments.

S.No.	Instrument	Model No.	Software	Manufactures name
1	HPLC Agilent	Agilent 1220 Infinity LC	Ezchrome(LC solutions)	Agilent
2	UV double beam spectrophotometer	PGIT60	UV Win Pro	Lab India
3	Digital weighing balance	-	-	Shimadzu
4	pH meter	-	-	Global Digital
5	Ultra sonicator	-	-	GlobalDigital

The experimental work involves several chemicals. Chemicals used presently are listed below:

Table -2 List of Chemicals.

S.No.	Chemicals	Manufacturer	Grade
1	Water	Merck	HPLC Grade
2	Methanol	Merck	HPLC Grade
3	Acetonitrile	Merck	HPLC Grade
4	Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate	Merck	A.R
5	Ofloxacin, Metronidazole API	-	-

HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT

Method development for simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole in Pharmaceutical dosage forms includes the following steps:

1. Selection of detection wavelength (λ_{max})
2. Selection of column
3. Selection of mobile phase
4. Selection of flow rate
5. Preparations and procedures

Selection of Detection wavelength:

10 mg of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole was dissolved in mobile phase. The solution was scanned from 200-400 nm the spectrum was obtained. The overlay spectrum was used for selection of wavelength for Ofloxacin and Metronidazole. The isobestic point was taken as detection wavelength.

Selection of column:

Column is selected based on solubility, polarity and chemical differences among Analytes [Column: Agilent C18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5 μ m)]

Selection of mobile phase:

Methanol: ACN (70:30%v/v) has been selected as mobile phase. If any buffer selected buffer pH should be between 2 to 8. If the buffer pH is below 2 siloxane linkages are cleaved. If the buffer pH is above 8 dissolution of silica takes place. pH controls the elution properties by controlling the ionization characteristics. It also decreases the retention and improves separation. Good Response, Area, Tailing factor, Resolution will be achieved.

Preparations and procedures:**Preparation of mobile phase:**

A mixture of Methanol 700 ml (70%), 300 mL of ACN (30%) are taken and degassed in ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes. Then this solution is filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluant Preparation:

Mobile phase is used as Diluant.

Preparation of the individual Ofloxacin standard preparation:

10mg of Ofloxacin working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and about 2ml of DMF is added. Then it is sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume upto the mark with the diluant. (Stock solution). Further 10.0 ml from the above stock solution is pipette into a 100 ml volumetric flask and was diluted upto the mark with diluant.

Preparation of the individual Metronidazole standard preparation:

10mg of Metronidazole working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and about 2ml of DMF is added. Then it is sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume upto the mark with the diluant. (Stock solution). Further 10.0 ml from the above stock solution is pipette into a 100 ml volumetric flask and was diluted upto the mark with diluant.

Preparation of Sample Solution :(Tablet)

Accurately 10 tablets are weighed and crushed in mortar and pestle and weight equivalent to 10 mg of Metronidazole and Ofloxacin (marketed formulation) sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluents is added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume upto the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution) Further 3 ml of above stock solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark with diluant.

Method Validation

The developed method was validated in terms of specificity, system suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantification and robustness.

Specificity Study

The specificity of the RP-HPLC method was checked by comparison of chromatograms obtained from standard, sample and the corresponding placebo.

Linearity and Range

The linearity of the method was determined at five concentration levels ranging from 10-50 μ g/mL for Ofloxacin and 10-50 μ g/mL for metronidazole. The calibration curves were constructed by plotting peak areas versus concentration of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole. The slope, Y-intercept and correlation coefficient were calculated.

Accuracy (% Recovery)

The accuracy of the method was evaluated in triplicate at three concentration levels, 50, 100 and 150 % of the target test concentration (10 μ g/mL of Ofloxacin and 10 μ g/mL of Metronidazole). The percentages of recoveries were calculated.

Precision

Precision was investigated using the sample preparation procedure for six pure samples of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole.

Method Precision (Intra-day): The precision of the method was evaluated by carrying out six independent assays of 10 μ g/mL of Ofloxacin and 10 μ g/mL of Metronidazole test samples against qualified reference standard. Six test samples were assayed against reference standard.

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were estimated using signal - to - noise ratio of 3:1 and 10:1 as per ICH guidelines.

Robustness

The robustness of the method was evaluated by assaying test solutions after slight but deliberate changes in the analytical conditions: Flow rate (± 0.2), column temperature ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$).

Ruggedness:

The ruggedness of the method was evaluated by two different analyst with different instruments and lab.

System-Suitability Test

The system suitability tests represent an integral part of the method and are used to ensure adequate performance of the chromatographic system. The parameters, retention time (RT), theoretical plates (N), tailing factor (T), peak asymmetry (As) and repeatability were evaluated using five replicate injections of the drugs at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Ofloxacin and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Metronidazole.

Forced Degradation or Stability Indicating Studies

Procedure: The specificity of the method can be demonstrated through forced degradation studies conducted on the sample using acid, alkaline, oxidative, thermal, photolytic, and UV degradations. The sample was exposed to these conditions and the main peak was studied for the peak purity

ACID DEGRADATION:

Forced degradation in acidic media was performed by adding 5 mL 0.1 M HCl to 10 mL of stock solution and the mixture is heated at 60°C for approximately 13hrs and the solution is neutralized by addition of 0.1 M NaOH. The prepared solution is injected and chromatograms were recorded.

ALKALINE DEGRADATION:

Forced degradation in basic media was performed by adding 5 mL 0.1 M NaOH to 10 mL of stock solution and the mixture is heated at 60°C for approximately 13hrs and the solution is neutralized by addition of 0.1 M HCl. The prepared solution is injected and chromatograms were recorded.

PHOTOLYTIC DEGRADATION:

Expose about 20 mg of sample in UV light chamber at 257 nm for 3 hrs. weigh accurately this power equivalent to 10 mg of ofloxacin and 10 mg of Metronidazole into a 100 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume and sonicate for 30 minutes with intermittent shaking and volume is made up to the mark with mobile phase and record the chromatogram.

THERMAL DEGRADATION:

Expose about 20mg of sample in to dry heat at 80°C for 13 hrs. weigh accurately this power equivalent to 10mg of ofloxacin and 10mg of metronidazole into a 100 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume and sonicate for 30 minutes with intermittent shaking and volume is made up to the mark with mobile phase and record the chromatogram.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To develop a precise, linear, specific & suitable stability indicating RP-HPLC method for analysis of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole in different chromatographic conditions were applied & the results observed are presented. Isocratic elution is simple, requires only one pump & flat baseline separation for easy and reproducible results. So, it was preferred for the current study over gradient elution & the results observed are presented (Shown in Table 3 and 4). The results of Correlation coefficient (r) LOD, LOQ, Accuracy, Precision, Robustness and Ruggedness are shown in Table 3. The results of System Suitability Parameters consisting of Retention time, Theoretical plates, Resolution are shown in Table 4. The standard chromatogram of degradation studies of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole bulk and dosage form are shown in figure 5. The calibration curve of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole is shown in Figure 3 and 4 respectively. Table.

Table 3: Results from Analysis and Calibration Curves.

Parameters	Ofloxacin	Metronidazole
Corelation coefficient(r)	0.999	0.999
LOD($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	2.95	3.04
LOQ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	9.87	10
ACCURACY	100%	100.5%
PRECISION	2.0	2.0
ROBUSTNESS	0.54	0.62
RUGGEDNESS	1.7	1.8

Table 4: Results of System Suitability Parameters.

Prametres	Ofloxacin	Metronidazole
Retention time	2.443	2.918
Theoretical plates	2114.5	2931.0
Tailing factor	1.7	1.7

Table 5: Results for Degradation studies of ofloxacin and metronidazole.

Stress Condition	Sample-1 (Ofloxacin)			Sample-2 (Metronidazole)		
	Area	%Assay	%Degradation	Area	%Assay	%Degradation
Acidic	110473	91.7	8.3	39575	92.4	7.6
Alkaline	124364	92.0	8.0	348679	89.7	11.3
Photolytic	113269	88.5	11.5	352392	87.5	12.5
Thermal	101474	96.3	3.7	352423	89.5	10.5
Oxidative	106734	94.3	5.7	382423	95.1	4.9

Fig-4 Calibration curve of Metronidazole.

Fig- 5 Assay of ofloxacin and metronidazole.

Fig-6A Chromatogram of Acid degradation sample.

Fig-6B Chromatogram of Alkali degradation sample.

Fig-6C Chromatogram of Oxidative degradation sample.

Fig-6D Chromatogram of Thermal degradation sample.

Fig-6E Chromatogram of Photolytic degradation of sample.

CONCLUSION

A sensitive & selective RP-HPLC method has been developed & validated for the analysis of Ofloxacin and Metronidazole in bulk dosage form. Further the proposed RP-HPLC method has excellent sensitivity, precision and reproducibility. The result shows the developed method is yet another suitable method for assay, impurity studies which can help in the analysis of Acetaminophen and Tramadol in different formulations.

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